

ISSUES OF EVALUATING THE ECONOMIC EFFECTIVENESS OF INNOVATION PROJECTS IN THE CONSTRUCTION FIELD

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7890670>

Abstract: In the construction materials industry of our republic, systematic work is being carried out aimed at ensuring stable growth in the production and export of competitive products, as well as modernization of enterprises, technical and technological updating. Innovation is not always about creating new technologies or materials, but about developing and improving what we already have.

Key words: building materials, modernization, innovation economy

In our country, the construction sector solves social, economic and technical issues and makes a great contribution to the development of the economy within the material production sectors. During the years of independence, important economic reforms were implemented in the construction sector. In the decision of the President of February 2, 2019 "On the measures of radical improvement and comprehensive development of the construction materials industry" in 2019-2021, the total cost is 1.3 billion, including direct at the expense of foreign investments, the task of implementing 67 investment projects for the technical and technological renewal of existing enterprises and the establishment of new enterprises in the amount of 692 million US dollars was set. The implementation of these and other projects will increase the capacity of cement production to 17 million tons by 2021, architectural and construction glass to 32 million square meters, chipboard (DSP) to 380,000, aerated concrete blocks to 700,000 For the construction of multi-storey houses, it is possible to supply 180,000 square meters of large-panel reinforced concrete products. The decision of the head of our state dated May 23, 2019 "On additional measures for the rapid development of the construction materials industry" defined the prospects and strategy of the industry for the near future. Its main goal is to create favorable conditions for the rapid development and diversification of the industry, to attract investments in the processing of local mineral resources, and to increase the volume of export of construction materials. As a result of the solution of these tasks, until 2025, the production volume of paperboards will increase by more than 47 times, assembled parquet panels and tiles - by 19 times, boards made of wood and other wood-based materials - by 15 times, aerated concrete blocks It is planned to increase by 7 times, architectural-building glass made on the basis of varnish-paint materials and energy and heat-saving float technology - by 4 times, composite fittings made of basalt - by 3 times, and by cement - by 2 times. In the construction sector, a wide path has been opened for small business and private entrepreneurship, and the infrastructure of market relations has been formed. This encouraged construction process participants in the implementation of innovative-investment projects and increased the competitiveness of construction organizations. As a result, the innovative investment attractiveness of the construction production organizations increased and made it possible to implement the

innovative policy. In construction production, various construction works and technological processes are carried out, and in these processes, various innovations, i.e. improvement of design processes on the basis of automation, creation of new modern technologies of building construction, implementation of new modern methods of construction management, new projects. An example of this is the model houses being built in rural areas. It should be noted that the buildings and structures being built in the construction sector are divided into civil and industrial groups. If we refer to the analysis, nowadays the demand of the population of our country for housing is increasing. From this point of view, the innovation projects implemented in the construction of residences in our country are at the center of our research. When we analyze the literature in our country and abroad, we see that the concepts of innovation and innovation evaluation are interpreted differently. This, in turn, requires the analysis and clarification of these concepts from the point of view of the construction of residential buildings. Today, "innovation", "renewal", "innovation", "innovation process", "innovation activity", "investment" and other concepts have firmly entered the organizational-legal and organizational-economic activities of enterprises and organizations. From this point of view, I think it is appropriate to bring the above concepts to a common denominator in a scientifically based case. If we refer to the international economic literature, "innovation" is interpreted from the point of view of creating new material wealth by applying scientific and technical results to practical activities. I think it is appropriate to distinguish the following aspects of "innovation", which represent different aspects: - innovation - ideas and innovations are put into practice and become economically significant. Scientific and technical innovation is a renewal process, which can be divided into productive and technical-market oriented types; - these are technical, production and commercial events, a complex of emergence of new and improved goods, services, processes and equipment on the market; - this is a collective, technical, economic process in which ideas and innovations are put into practice, and material goods are created that satisfy the tastes and desires of customers according to their characteristics and quality indicators, and bring economic benefits to the consumer. and extra for the market creates value.

- innovation - the initial structure of the production organism is changed and the internal structure is updated.

- innovation is a quantitative and qualitative change in the activity of a specific industry enterprise. There are other definitions of innovation. All definitions can be summarized in the following two approaches. First, innovation is the result of a creative process, an existing product, technology,

methods or, secondly, new items, elements, approaches, principles. Summarizing the definitions of different authors, innovation is a practical expression of a new scientific idea applied to the production of goods or the provision of services for a specific subject.

The result of this may be a new model of technology, the development of new building materials or some kind of supplement for them, a new way of organizing or managing work in construction, etc. According to its approach, innovations are technical, technological, economic, organizational,

- it can be in management and other forms. Based on the above definitions of innovation, innovation for residential project construction practice can be defined according to the following classification symbols.

- decreasing operating costs during the life cycle of residences, for example, the criterion of maintaining a constant temperature inside the apartment by saving costs as a result of using heat-retaining wall materials;
- equipping with modern economical air conditioning and ventilation equipment;
- development and implementation of import-substituting building materials, products and constructions based on local raw materials;
- improvement of project and constructive solutions based on the geographical location of the territories and changes.

Innovations can be interpreted in terms of production, use and exploitation, depending on the end consumer. As a result of the use of production innovations in the organizations of the construction industry, efficiency leads to organizational, management or technological efficiency, as well as the implementation of new techniques and technologies. As a result, effort and time are saved. Consumers of innovations in use are private individuals and organizations that build buildings and structures and use them based on their goals. Examples of these include the use of new materials and products, architectural and constructive solutions.

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